

**СТАН РЕСУСНОГО ЗАБЕЗПЕЧЕННЯ ЗАКЛАДІВ ОХОРОНИ
ЗДОРОВ'Я м. КИЇВ ЯК ОСНОВА ЗАПРОВАДЖЕННЯ
КАРДІОРЕАБІЛІТАЦІЇ**

**STATE OF RESOURCE PROVISION OF HEALTHCARE
INSTITUTIONS OF KYIV AS A BASIS FOR THE INTRODUCTION OF
CARDIOLOGICAL REHABILITATION**

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Diseases of the circulatory system are the leading cause of death in the world. The loss of human life and the significant direct and indirect costs of health care are the results of cardiovascular disease. Cardiac rehabilitation is considered a key component of secondary prevention for patients with cardiovascular disease, aimed at reducing the risk of death from these diseases, unplanned hospitalization and recurrent myocardial infarction.

The Law of Ukraine "On Rehabilitation in the Field of Health Care" was adopted in December 2020. The provisions of the law require an adequate response from the heads of health care facilities, in particular, the provision of resources for cardiac rehabilitation.

In order to study the initial conditions for the cardiac rehabilitation of Kyiv residents in need of rehabilitation treatment after cardiac events, an analysis of the resource base of health care facilities in Kyiv was conducted.

It is established that the network of institutions that used rehabilitation technologies in their activities is formed by 15 cardiology departments with a capacity of 700 beds, 17 rehabilitation departments, 60 physiotherapy departments, 21 speech therapy rooms, 13 physical therapy rooms, and 4 psychotherapy rooms. The human resources included 208 cardiologists, 4 nutritionists, 79 physiotherapists, 21 doctors

from therapeutic physical education, 4 reflexologists, 20 psychotherapists, 48 psychologists, 81 speech therapists, 14,689 nurses.

Health care facilities are provided with rehabilitation facilities in the amount of 50.0% to 100.0%.

Financial support for rehabilitation care is provided by reimbursement from the National Health Service of Ukraine as part of treatment packages for acute stroke and myocardial infarction.

Medical standards and clinical protocols for the treatment of these diseases include evidence-based rehabilitation measures. Evidence-based technologies for the rehabilitation of other diseases of the cardiovascular system have not been developed.

Conclusion. Human, infrastructural, logistical, technological resources exist within the existing system of rehabilitation care. These resources form the basis for the establishment of rehabilitation hospitals, outpatient rehabilitation institutions, comprehensive rehabilitation institutions, inpatient and outpatient departments of post-acute and long-term rehabilitation by reorganizing them in the manner permitted by law.

However, they are subject to transformation in accordance with changes in legislation. It is necessary to retrain specialists in the field of cardiac rehabilitation, in particular, physical therapists, to introduce a multidisciplinary approach to cardiac rehabilitation and the use of evidence-based and telemedicine technologies.